

Energy System Modelling Using OSeMOSYS

Development of a national energy system model – Activity 2

Please use the following citation for:

- **This Activity**

Plazas-Niño, F., Alexander K. (2024, April). Energy System Modelling Using OSeMOSYS: Development of a national energy system model – Activity 2 (Version 1.0).

- **OSeMOSYS UI Software**

Climate Compatible Growth. (2024). MUIO (Version v5.0.0). GitHub. <https://github.com/ClimateCompatibleGrowth/MUIO>

- **OSeMOSYS Google Forum**

If you are stuck, please ask questions [here](#). If you get ahead, please answer questions in the same forum. Please state that you are using the 'OSeMOSYS UI' and not 'ClicSAND'.

Tasks

N.B. In order to carry out this activity and all the ones that follow in the course, you need a computer that has Windows 10 Operating System or later.

Through this activity, you will install the Modelling User Interface for OSeMOSYS (MUIO) you will be using for creating models throughout the course.

To install the MUIO:

1. Download the latest version of the user interface from [here](#).
2. Move the .exe file from your download folder to a folder where you have administrator privileges. This may be for instance inside the folder: **users>>name_of_the_user** or any other folder you prefer.

3. Right-click on osemosys.exe and click **'Run as administrator'**. This will start the installation of the MUIO. The installation may take several minutes. Once it is complete, the installation window will simply disappear.
4. Once the installation has been completed, open the installation folder (i.e., C:\Users\your_user_name\AppData\Local\osemosys) and find the file 'osemosys.exe'. Right-click on it and **'Run as administrator'**.
5. You will see the MUIO in a new window.